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D3.1.3 Searchable online RMs catalogue

The CARE Collection: A searchable online catalog of microbiological reference materials (RMs) dedicated to zoonotic and foodborne bacterial pathogens

Microbiological Reference materials (RMs) are perfectly characterized microbial strains considered as essential components for quality control, validation of new methods, proficiency testing (PT) and the advancement of science. The CARE joint integrative project aims to create a collection of foodborne pathogenic bacterial strains easily findable and accessible that can be used as RMs.

For creating the CARE collection, a list of seven major pathogenic bacterial species across Europe was compiled namely *Campylobacter*, *Yersinia*, *Salmonella*, *Staphylococcus*, *Escherichia*, *Bacillus* and *Listeria*. This was followed by setting up of criteria for traceability and strain characteristics by experts, to qualify the strains as RM. Thus, the CARE collection was made of resources available within the CARE Consortium. A database associated with a web portal has now been created offering Search, Order and RM Deposit functionalities. Importantly, the physical CARE collection will be maintained, stored and made accessible under certified quality standards via three microbial Biological Resource Centers (mBRCs), members of the One Health EJP consortium, guaranteeing sustainability.

In its current state, the CARE collection consists of 548 bacterial strains, from seven bacterial species that are crucial and of high priority in the European Union. Their distribution is as shown in Figure 1. Each RM is associated with metadata about its origin, relevant phenotypic (including antimicrobial resistance profile) characteristics and genomic information. All CARE catalog entries are Nagoya compliant and their integration into the mBRCs catalogs are underway.

CARE RM Species Distribution

Figure 1.1: Species distribution of RMs in CARE Collection

Species	Number of RMs
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i>	54
<i>Yersinia pseudotuberculosis</i>	5
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	137
<i>Bacillus toyonensis</i>	3
<i>Bacillus mycoides</i>	2
<i>Bacillus wiedmannii</i>	1
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	21
<i>Bacillus pacificus</i>	1
<i>Bacillus paranthracis</i>	2
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	60
<i>Salmonella bongori</i>	1
<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	88
<i>Campylobacter coli</i>	28
<i>Campylobacter lari</i>	1
<i>Campylobacter lanienae</i>	1
<i>Campylobacter fetus</i>	1
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	52
<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	105

Figure 1.2: Review of pathogen species currently in the CARE database

Detail about the providers and potential RM distributors

RM species	ANSES	IP	INRAE	ISS	IZSLER	IZSAM	PIWET	VISAVET	RIVM	SVA	SLV	DTU	BRCs for deposits
Salmonella (293) / 1104 inventoried	25 (55)	121	32		2		36	8	12	2			IP/INRAE/BVR
Listeria (130) / 105 inventoried	23 (85)			22									INRAE/BVR
Campylo (95 +20) / 561 inventoried				3		3		77	+20	8	2	2	INRAE
E. coli (81) / 315 inventoried				18	23			35		2		3	BVR
Staph (108) / 685 inventoried	31		5	15	21			30		6			IP/INRAE/BVR
B. cereus (30) / 26 inventoried	11		13				6						IP/INRAE
Yersinia (59) / 150 inventoried		22		7				30					IP/BVR
Contact person for the DMP	AB	OC	EH	VM (SM)	MBB	GA	MZ	VLC (MUR)	HA	HS	HR	RH	219 INRAE 215 IP 242 BVR

Total = 293 + 130 + 115 + 81 + 108 + 30 + 59 = **816** strains of which **676** would be deposited

AB : Anne [Brisabois](#)
 OC : Olivier [Chesneau](#)
 HR : Hilde [Riedel](#)

VM : Valeria [Michelacci](#)
 GA : Giuseppe [Aprea](#)
 MZ : Magdalena [Zajac](#)

HA : Henk [Aarts](#)
 HS : Hanna [Skarin](#)
 RH : Rene [Hendriksen](#)

MBB : Maria-Beatrice [Boniotti](#)
 VLC : Vicente Lopez-[Chavarrias](#)
 EH : Emmanuelle [Helloin](#)

1. CARE Database

- The CARE database is built using the biological database management commercial software Biologics produced by [BioAware](#) SA NV, based in Belgium. The relational scheme of the DB can be represented as follows:

Figure 2: Schema of the CARE Collection comprising of the database and Web Portal

- The Collection of RMs is isolated from Plants, Animals, Humans, Environment, Food, and Agro-Industrial environments (including food production and processing units).
- The entire collection is very well characterized and includes information in 23 mandatory fields including information on Taxonomy, Meta data, Literature, Growth conditions, WGS data, and Contact details of RM Providers and Host mBRCs. All this information was collated on Species-specific and partner-specific Google sheets (RM Data Sheets).

The tentative data import process to be followed, to import RM data from RM data sheets, into CARE database (Biologics software) is:

- Assigning CARE IDs
- Generate .CSV subfiles for import (using titles as per Row 3 in Google sheets):
 - IDs + Taxonomy + PT related info + Metadata (except Nagoya Protocol)
 - CARE ID + Literature + Molecular Data including WGS data, and molecular typing data, (except Virulence markers) + RM Provider + Additional comments

- CARE ID + Virulence markers + AMR Profile (pre-step: split data into individual cells for fields "Virulence markers", "AMR genes in silico", and "AMR Pattern by phenotypic determination")
 - CARE ID + selected columns from output excel sheets of starAMR WGS analysis pipeline (pre-step: match Provider RM Id with CARE Id --> import data starAMR data into Google sheets)
 - CARE ID + Culture & growth conditions + Nagoya Protocol + Ordering Information
3. Import data into Biologics using the .csv subfiles

The screenshot displays the Biologics software interface. The main window shows a table of RM strains with columns: id, CARE ID, Read groups, Location of Sampling, and Name of Strain. The table contains 42 rows of data. On the right side, a 'Fields' panel is open, showing a hierarchical list of fields associated with the selected record (CARE_00001). The fields include: Description, Rights on the record, e1158: Reference IDs in other collections, Species Taxonomy (with sub-fields like olink1173: Name of Strain, rlink1207: Subspecies, rlink1174: Serotype, e1162: Biovar/ Pathovar), Proficiency Testing related information (with sub-fields like v1229: Relevant type of Proficiency Testing, v1238: Reason to include the strain in the list, e1289: Additional comments for justification as RM), Meta Data (with sub-fields like v1164: Biosafety Level, v1237: Additional regulations applicable, v1171: Context of Sample Isolation, v1170: Sector of Sample Collection, rlink1176: Matrix/ Source, olink1210: Location of Sampling, h1168: Date of Sample Collection, h1169: Date of Pathogen Isolation, v1172: Nagoya protocol compliance conditions, flink1185: Supplementary Documents), Literature, Culture Conditions (with sub-fields like e1290: Growth Medium, e1291: Growth Temperatures, flink1292: Growth Medium Recipes, e1293: Additional information on culture conditions), and Molecular Data (with sub-fields like rlink1217: WGS Data, (1) Record(57), Description, Rights on the record, u1216: WGS sequencing data raw reads, u1243: WGS Assembly Data, u1294: MD 16S Sequence, u1295: MLST Type, u1296: MLVA type).

id	CARE ID	Read groups	Location of Sampling	Name of Strain
1	CARE_00001	Administrators, Internet users	Mordelles	Yersinia enterocolitica
2	CARE_00002	Administrators, Internet users, Woippy		Yersinia enterocolitica
3	CARE_00003	Administrators, Internet users, Metz		Yersinia enterocolitica
4	CARE_00004	Administrators, Internet users, Limoges		Yersinia enterocolitica
5	CARE_00005	Administrators, Internet users, Muret		Yersinia pseudotuberculosis
6	CARE_00006	Administrators, Internet users, Primorski		Yersinia pseudotuberculosis
7	CARE_00007	Administrators, Internet users, Lille		Yersinia enterocolitica
8	CARE_00008	Administrators, Internet users, La Réunion (Sainte Clotilde)		Yersinia enterocolitica
9	CARE_00009	Administrators, Internet users, Saumur		Yersinia enterocolitica
10	CARE_00010	Administrators, Internet users, Tours		Yersinia enterocolitica
11	CARE_00011	Administrators, Internet users, Coquelles		Yersinia enterocolitica
12	CARE_00012	Administrators, Internet users, Orsay		Yersinia enterocolitica
13	CARE_00013	Administrators, Internet users, Brumath		Yersinia enterocolitica
14	CARE_00014	Administrators, Internet users, Muret		Yersinia enterocolitica
15	CARE_00015	Administrators, Internet users, Besançon		Yersinia enterocolitica
16	CARE_00016	Administrators, Internet users, Belgium		Yersinia enterocolitica
17	CARE_00017	Administrators, Internet users, Montauban		Yersinia enterocolitica
18	CARE_00018	Administrators, Internet users, Novosibirsk		Yersinia pseudotuberculosis
19	CARE_00019	Administrators, Internet users, Khabarovsk		Yersinia pseudotuberculosis
20	CARE_00020	Administrators, Internet users, Montfavet		Yersinia pseudotuberculosis
21	CARE_00021	Administrators, Internet users, Montpellier		Yersinia enterocolitica
22	CARE_00022	Administrators, Internet users, Vaires sur Marnes		Yersinia enterocolitica
23	CARE_00023	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus wiedmannii
24	CARE_00024	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus cereus
25	CARE_00025	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus cereus
26	CARE_00026	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus cereus
27	CARE_00027	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus cereus
28	CARE_00028	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus pacificus
29	CARE_00029	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus cereus
30	CARE_00030	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus cereus
31	CARE_00031	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus toyonensis
32	CARE_00032	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus paranthracis
33	CARE_00033	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus cereus
34	CARE_00034	Administrators, Internet users, Chambéry		Bacillus cereus
35	CARE_00035	Administrators, Internet users, Grenoble		Bacillus cereus
36	CARE_00036	Administrators, Internet users, Grenoble		Bacillus cereus
37	CARE_00037	Administrators, Internet users, Grenoble		Bacillus cereus
38	CARE_00038	Administrators, Internet users, Grenoble		Bacillus cereus
39	CARE_00039	Administrators, Internet users, Chambéry		Bacillus cereus
40	CARE_00040	Administrators, Internet users, France		Bacillus mycoides
41	CARE_00041	Administrators, Internet users, Normandie		Bacillus cereus
42	CARE_00042	Administrators, Internet users, Normandie		Bacillus cereus

Figure 3: View of the RM strains in the CARE Database with all fields associated with the RM alongside (on Biologics software)

CARE_00001

Fields	Values
Description	[1] CARE_00001
Rights on the record	
e1158: Reference IDs in other collections	
Species Taxonomy	
olink1173: Name of Strain	Yersinia enterocolitica [Strain Taxonomy]
rlink1207: Subspecies	2-3/9b [Subspecies]
rlink1174: Serotype	O:9 [Serotypes]
e1162: Biovar/ Pathovar	
Proficiency Testing related information	
v1229: Relevant type of Proficiency Testing	Undefined
v1238: Reason to include the strain in the list	Strain is used as reference for AMR
e1289: Additional comments for justification as RM	
Meta Data	
v1164: Biosafety Level	2
v1237: Additional regulations applicable	Undefined
v1171: Context of Sample Isolation	Human clinical
v1170: Sector of Sample Collection	Human
rlink1176: Matrix/ Source	Stools [Sources of Samples]
olink1210: Location of Sampling	Mordelles [Location of Sampling]
h1168: Date of Sample Collection	2019
h1169: Date of Pathogen Isolation	?
v1172: Nagoya protocol compliance conditions	Not under the scope of the Nagoya protocol
flink1185: Supplementary Documents	
Literature	
Culture Conditions	
e1290: Growth Medium	TSB
e1291: Growth Temperatures	30
flink1292: Growth Medium Recipes	
e1293: Additional information on culture conditions	
Molecular Data	
rlink1217: WGS Data	ERR6281559 [Whole Genome Sequencing Data]
(1) Record[57]	ERR6281559
Description	[57] ERR6281559
Rights on the record	
u1216: WGS sequencing data raw reads	1 record displayed (100%); https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERR6281559?show=reads (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERR6281559?show=reads)
u1243: WGS Assembly Data	0 record displayed (0%)
u1294: MD 16S Sequence	0 record displayed (0%)
u1295: MLST Type	0 record displayed (0%)
u1296: MLVA type	0 record displayed (0%)

Tree view Form view

Figure 4.1: View of all fields associated with the RM CARE_00001 in the CARE Database (on Biolomics software)

Fields	Values
h1169: Date of Pathogen Isolation	?
v1172: Nagoya protocol compliance conditions	Not under the scope of the Nagoya protocol
flink1185: Supplementary Documents	
Literature	
Culture Conditions	
e1290: Growth Medium	TSB
e1291: Growth Temperatures	30
flink1292: Growth Medium Recipes	
e1293: Additional information on culture conditions	
Molecular Data	
rlink1217: WGS Data	ERR6281559 [Whole Genome Sequencing Data]
(1) Record[57]	ERR6281559
Description	[57] ERR6281559
Rights on the record	
u1216: WGS sequencing data raw reads	1 record displayed (100%): https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERR6281559?show=reads (https://w...
u1243: WGS Assembly Data	0 record displayed (0%)
u1294: MD 16S Sequence	0 record displayed (0%)
u1295: MLST Type	0 record displayed (0%)
u1296: MLVA type	0 record displayed (0%)
e1297: ST or CC type	
rlink1215: MALDI-TOF Data	
v1197: Possibility of getting MALDI-TOF spectra	Yes
rlink1219: Virulence Markers	pV plasmid [Virulence Markers]
(1) Record[3]	pV plasmid
Antimicrobial Resistance Profile	
Supplier Information	
e1181: Provider RM ID	IP42547
v1239: Provider Organization	Undefined
rlink1212: Provider Contact	Anne-Sophie Le Guern [Suppliers]
(1) Record[1]	Anne-Sophie Le Guern
Description	[1] Anne-Sophie Le Guern
Rights on the record	
e1189: Contact Email of Provider	anne-sophie.le-guern@pasteur.fr
e1240: Host mBRC RM ID	
v1179: Host mBRC Organization	Collection of Institut Pasteur - France
rlink1304: Host mBRC Contact	
v1188: Format of Supply	Undefined
u1218: Link to the strain on host mBRC website	0 record displayed (0%)
e1206: Additional Comments	

Figure 4.2: View of all fields associated with the RM CARE_00001 in the CARE Database (on Biologics software) (contd).

2. CARE Web Portal

The CARE Web Portal has been developed using the Biologics web development software.

In its current state, the CARE Web Portal is in its beta version with basic content and functionalities developed for the web pages **Homepage**, **Search**, **Order**, and **Deposit**.

Figure 5.1: Homepage of CARE Web Portal

Figure 5.2: Homepage of CARE Web Portal (contd)

Figure 5.3: Homepage of CARE Web Portal (cont.)

2.1 SEARCH

On the Search Page, the user can make a Simple Search using the name of the desired strain, or using an Advanced Search where they can filter on the basis of Location, Sector, AMR profiles, Virulence genes, etc. The user can select the desired RM using the tick boxes alongside each of them, and can export the selected list to be downloaded as a PDF document.

Figure 6: Search page of CARE Web Portal

2.2 ORDER

On the Order Page, the user can access the contact details of the mBRCs, the different pricing plans for RMs, and the procedure for placing the order. They can refer to the information of Host mBRCs for their desired RM, accordingly contact and send the exported PDF document of Selected List of RMs to the respective mBRC.

The screenshot displays the 'OUR PRICING PLANS' section of the CARE Web Portal. At the top, it states: 'The CARE collection of RMs is maintained and conserved in three mBRCs. To order stains you have to directly contact the mBRC in charge of the strains of your interest.' Below this, three contact points are listed: 'Collection of Institut Pasteur CIP : cip@pasteur.fr', 'Biobank of veterinary resources BVR IZSLER : substr@izsler.it', and 'CIRM-BP : cirm_bp-tours@inra.fr'. The main heading is 'OUR PRICING PLANS' in red. A note below reads: 'Freight and handling charges in addition to the net price will be applied.' Three pricing cards are shown: 'BASIC' with '100€' and '1 Strain'; 'MULTIPLE' with '-10%' and '10 Strains'; and 'CARE PARTNERS' with '70€' and '1 Strain'.

Figure 7.1: Order page of CARE Web Portal

Proposed Pricing

A net price of 100 EUR is charged per strain

A 10% reduced rate will be applied when ordering 10 strains - (To be discussed)

A special price of 70 EUR is offered to CARE partners - (To be discussed)

Freight and handling charges in addition to the net price will be applied.

Warning on the use of strains will be stipulated on the order page (To be discussed with legal affairs department)

All cultures supplied by CARE Catalog are, to the best of our knowledge, free of background IP or ownership issues which prevent or restrict scientific research associated with those cultures. Should there be any pre-conditions attached to the release or use of an CARE culture outside those already stipulated in our standard Material Transfer Agreement (MTA), we will inform the purchaser in advance.

It is ultimately the responsibility of the end user to ensure that any development, commercial exploitation or use of cultures supplied does not infringe patent or other IP or ownership rights already granted, or have any obligations with regard to the country of origin as laid down in the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD).

- 1 Select and export lists of your RM strains of interest**

On the Search Page of the CARE website, select your desired strains by using the tick-boxes alongside each RM. Make sure to select and export separate documents for each mBRC, in case your selected RM list contains strains that are hosted by different mBRCs.
- 2 Contact the relevant mBRC with your requirements**

In order to know which mBRC you must contact, please refer to the "Host mBRC organization" field in the RM strain associated data.

Send an email to the relevant mBRC sharing the list of strains exported through the website.
- 3 Sign the Material Transfer Agreement (MTA)**

Upon receipt of your strain requirements, the contacted mBRC will revert to you to attend to your queries and send an MTA agreement.

Orders will only be validated by the mBRC after the completed and signed MTA has been received in duplicate, along with a signed purchase order. A countersigned agreement will then be returned with the strain(s) thus ordered.

Figure 7.2: Process of ordering RM from the Order page of CARE Web Portal

2.3 DEPOSIT

On the Deposit Page, the user can access the procedure for placing the order.

1 Step 1: STRAIN INFORMATION

- The depositor contacts the CARE Catalogue via abcd@inrae.fr
- The depositor transmits all information on the strains concerned, including their identity, characterization, origin, etc., using the Acquisition Form.
- The depositor is informed that the CARE maintains a collection of food-associated bacteria, its mission being to preserve the strains deposited and their associated data. The strains will thus become available to the scientific community for research, development, teaching, and identification.

2 Step 2: VALIDATION

3 Step 3: INTEGRATION

Next

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Figure 8.1: Process of depositing RM from the Deposit page of CARE Web Portal

Step 1: STRAIN INFORMATION

2 Step 2: VALIDATION

- Depending on the data related to the strains, the CARE validates their inclusion in their open collection.
- The depositor agrees to :
 - distribution of the strains (under an MTA issued by the CARE according to the ECCO core-MTA), and
 - research and characterization being performed on the strains.
- The depositor is informed that if any commercial applications are developed as a result of research conducted on the strains, the depositor will be assured a fair and equitable return based on current ABS (Access and Benefit-sharing) regulations.

Step 3: INTEGRATION

Back Next

Figure 8.2: Process of depositing RM from the Deposit page of CARE Web Portal (cont.)

Step 1: STRAIN INFORMATION

Step 2: VALIDATION

3 Step 3: INTEGRATION

- The acquisition form is validated and allocated a unique identifier (CARE ID n°).
- After reception of the strains and signature of the acquisition form, the purity of strains is verified and they are frozen and freeze-dried.
- A certificate of deposit is sent to the depositor together with two vials of each freeze-dried strain.
- For an open deposit, the CARE becomes the Host mBRC of the strains but never the owner. If commercial applications are developed as a result of research using the strains, a fair and equitable sharing of any profits is guaranteed to the DEPOSITOR, based on the current ABS regulations.
- Deposit of a strain in the CARE collection is free of charge, but the CARE can refuse a deposit based on the originality of the strain, the quality, and extent of its characterization, or for other reasons (i.e., not being food-associated, specific culture conditions, etc).
- There is a charge for the safe deposit of strains. For your convenience, the safe deposit contract may permit restricted access to some of your partners, according to terms and conditions defined by you as the applicant.

Back Finish

Figure 8.3: Process of depositing RM from the Deposit page of CARE Web Portal (contd)

The implementation of the CARE catalog is a joint effort of 13 European public health-, veterinary-, and research institutes. This unique initiative to collect and share food safety related zoonotic RMs isolated from humans, animals, food or the environment will substantially contribute to the harmonization of scientific activities within the European laboratories that work within the area from a one health perspective.

3. CURRENT STATUS

The CARE Collection is currently in its Beta version. We plan to put the collection online once a significant number of RMs have been transferred to the mBRCs. The collection will be accessible to the CARE partners from 15 May 2022, for their feedback and iterations. The final collection will be open to public by mid-July 2022.

- All the WGS data available are being analyzed computationally to determine genetic AMR profiles of all RMs using WGS data analysis pipeline StarAMR (<https://github.com/phac-nml/staramr>) based on ResFinder DB. The output will be integrated into the CARE database.
- Information regarding genetic AMR profiles for RMs, as shared by the RM providers, requires additional data processing to make it compatible for importing into the database. Hence we are currently developing scripts to automate this data processing. Once the scripts are developed, we will use them to process existing AMR data, and integrate into the CARE database.
- We are in the process of further developing and refining the content, and defining the visualization of RM data on the Web Portal.